

AN INVESTIGATION INTO STRESS MANAGEMENT APPROACHES AMONG SELF-FINANCING ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE EDUCATORS IN KERALA

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Abstract

Teacher stress can be characterized as the experience of unpleasant, negative emotions such as anger, anxiety, tension, frustration, or depression, which arise from aspects of an educator's professional responsibilities. The stress in teaching has been getting a fair degree of stress in recent years. This study examines the stress management strategies adopted by self-financing arts and science college teachers. A survey was conducted with 50 teachers from various self-financing institutions. The study explores the key sources of stress, the coping mechanisms utilized, and the implications for well-being and academic achievement. Findings indicate that teachers experience multi-dimensional stress from both on-campus and off-campus factors.

(Stress, Coping mechanism, Occupational Stress)

INTRODUCTION

Educators demonstrate a heightened awareness of their behaviours and alignment with human principles, and are viewed as a fundamental component of an effective educational framework. A teacher has often been attributed to be a physically wearing and psychologically stressful occupation. A teacher who is satisfied with his job can perform his duty effectively and efficiently. And has a positive attitude towards teaching. But if he is under stress he can't work effectively and has a negative attitude towards his job. High stress can cause teachers to leave the profession. Stress can lead to illness and absenteeism. At present the teachers are suffering from changing job condition, insecurity in job, poor salary, biasness in promotion, work over load, role conflicts etc. Stress is a significant concern among college and university faculty, though research on this topic has often overlooked the unique dimensions of stress experienced by marginalized groups such as African American faculty (Thompson & Dey, 1998).

Teaching is widely recognized as a demanding profession, often accompanied by significant levels of stress. This is especially true for self-financing teachers, who operate within private institutions and are responsible for securing their own financial stability. These educators face unique challenges, including job

insecurity, pressure to meet performance targets, and the need to continually prove their worth to retain their positions. The stress experienced by self-financing teachers can stem from various sources, including heavy workloads, lack of institutional support, limited job security, and the need to balance teaching with administrative responsibilities. Unlike their counterparts in government-funded institutions, these teachers often work under precarious conditions, with limited access to benefits such as tenure, healthcare, and pensions.

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Effective stress management is crucial for self-financing teachers to maintain their well-being, job satisfaction, and overall effectiveness in the classroom. Without proper strategies to cope with stress, these educators may experience burnout, decreased productivity, and adverse effects on their mental and physical health. The term "stress management" encompasses a broad range of methods and psychotherapies intended to reduce or manage an individual's level of stress, particularly chronic stress. Reducing stress is the goal of stress management. While there are many symptoms associated with stress, they differ depending on the individual and are a normal part of life.

This study helps to understand the reasons and symptoms of teachers stress and methods adopted by them to overcome their professional stress. It also gives an idea of what is stress and the definition of stress. This helps to understand the concept of stress management and check the degree of stress undergone by college teachers of self-financing colleges and studying the stress management techniques adopted by the management and teachers.

Literature Review

Afzal, S., Din, M., & Qureshi, I. A. (2018) This study aimed to compare the stress levels of faculty at public and private universities. The Glazer stress assessment instrument, which comprises twenty sets of contrasting work experience questions, was utilized to evaluate the stress levels of the participants. A total of 307 teachers from public and private universities in Islamabad were included as the sample. The findings revealed that a majority of university teachers reported experiencing high levels of stress. While public sector university teachers exhibited moderate stress levels, their counterparts in private institutions exhibited a high degree of work-related stress. No significant differences were observed in the stress levels between male and female teachers. The implications suggest that private universities should implement measures to assist their faculty in managing stress, such as providing counselling, workshops, and seminars focused on stress control techniques for both teachers and students, enabling them to prioritize student progress more effectively.

Abirami, V. (2012). The modern world, often described as a world of achievements, is also a world brimming with stress. Stress can be found in various facets of life, whether within the family, business organizations, or any other social or economic context. From the moment of birth until the last breath, individuals are inevitably exposed to diverse stressful situations. Stress arises whenever one's mind and body

react to real or perceived circumstances. Given that every situation or event in our daily lives causes some degree of stress, it is unrealistic and impractical to eliminate stress from one's life. In fact, moderate levels of stress can be beneficial, helping individuals stay alert and perform well. The only individuals truly free from stress are those who have passed on. Dr. Hans Selye, the renowned expert on stress research, made the crucial distinction between harmful stress and beneficial stress. Harmful stress can lead to feelings of helplessness, frustration, and disappointment, and it can also result in physical and psychological damage, which Selye termed as "distress."

Sukumar, M. A., & Kanagarathinam, M. (2016). The earliest description of the body's response to stress was made by renowned scientist Walter Cannon in 1914, which is when stress studies got their start. He recognised the automatic "fight or flight" response that arises in emergency situations when a person must face or escape a perilous situation. It used to be thought of as a relatively low-stress profession where academic members had advantages like tenure, light workloads, flexibility, and chances to study and attend conferences abroad. Nonetheless, new research indicates that college instructors are among the most stressed-out professional groups. With data gathered from five departments in private colleges, the current study sought to investigate how faculty members perceived occupational stress using a pre-established questionnaire. The purpose of the study was to identify stressors, explore stress-reduction strategies used by college instructors, and comprehend faculty perspectives on teaching and student management.

Gartia, R., & Sharma, S. (2013). This study examined the stressors that teacher educators who work in independently funded education colleges connected to Kurukshetra University in Haryana face daily. Time management, stresses associated to the job, professional anguish, motivation and discipline, and professional investment were the five main causes of stress among teachers that were investigated. A representative sample of 85 teacher educators, consisting of 56 females and 29 males, was chosen at random from 12 self-financing colleges. The modified version of the Fimian Teacher Stress Inventory, which showed an alpha Cronbach reliability of .85, was used by the researchers to gauge teacher stress. Statistical analyses that were both descriptive and inferential were used. The results show that gender has no discernible impact on teacher stress levels. Significant variations in stress levels were noted, nevertheless, between teacher educators who instruct fifty or more students in a class, between those who instruct fewer than four periods daily and those who instruct more than four periods daily, and between those who have three or more years of experience teaching and those who have less than three years.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The rapid growth of self-financing arts and science colleges in India has been driven by the increasing demand for higher education and limited public funding. However, research on the experiences of faculty at these institutions, including the stresses they face and their stress management strategies, is scarce. Existing studies on faculty stress have primarily focused on public universities, while the unique challenges encountered by those in the self-financing college setting have been largely neglected.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

In the modern world, stress is an unavoidable aspect of existence. Both the pleasure and difficulty of life increase. When a person's stress level surpasses their capacity for adjustment, it disrupts their life. Stress arises from both personal and organisational factors. It follows that stress is a normal occurrence and that its effects can be either beneficial or detrimental, depending on how it is handled. The purpose of this

study is to investigate coping strategies and stress levels among college instructors at self-financing colleges affiliated to University of Calicut.

OBJECTIVES

- To identify the key sources of stress among self-financing arts and science college teachers.
- To study the effects of stress among college teachers in self-financing colleges.
- To analyze the coping mechanism adopted by the teachers to reduce the stress.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study involved surveying a sample of 50 teachers from diverse arts and science self-financing colleges located in Palakkad District. The data were collected through an online questionnaire.

Sample Techniques

The study utilized a convenience sampling approach to select participants

Data Collection & Analysis

The research incorporated both primary and secondary data sources. The primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to faculty members from self-financing arts and science colleges. Secondary data were gathered from academic journals, research publications, and online resources. The data were analysed using simple percentage analysis.

Results & Interpretation

Table 1 Distribution of Age wise Classification

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
20 - 30	8	16
30- 40	21	42
40 - 50	15	30
Above 50	6	12
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: Table-1 shows the age of the respondents. Out of 50 respondents that is 42% are belonging to 30-40 age group. 12% are belongs to above 50 age group.

Table 2 Distribution of Gender wise Classification

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Male	17	34
Female	33	66
Others	0	0
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: Table 2 shows that the gender of respondents. Here 66% are female and 34 % are male.

Table 3 Distribution of Marital Status

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Married	33	66
Unmarried	17	34
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 66% respondents are married and 34% unmarried.

Table 4 Distribution of Educational qualification

Option	No of respondents	Percentage
NET	32	64
PhD	9	18
PG	8	16
B. Ed	1	2
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 64% respondents have the qualification Net. 18% having PhD and 16% PG qualified and 2% qualified is B. Ed.

Table 5 Distribution of Designation

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Assistant professor	48	96
Associate professor	2	4
Professor	0	0
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: In the above table 96% respondents are Assistant professors and only 4% are Associate professors.

Table 6 Distribution of Income

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
20000- 40000	38	76
40000- 60000	7	14
Above 60000	5	10
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: Table 5 shows the income of the respondents. 76% of the respondents are in the group of 20000-40000; 14% of the respondents are in the income group of 40000 - 60000 and only 10% having more than 60000.

Table 6 Distribution of Work load

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	26	52
Agree	22	44
Neutral	1	2
Disagree	1	2
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table ,52% respondents are strongly agreed that they have high degree of work load And 44% agreed they too have workload related stress and only 2 % have neutral opinion and other 2% disagree

Table 6 Distribution tends to quit the Job

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	15	30
Agree	29	58
Neutral	5	10
Disagree	1	2
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 58% of respondents are agreed with stress tends to quite job. 30% strongly agrees to the fact, only 10 % have neutral answer and no one strongly disagrees.

Table 7 Distribution Activities undertake during working day

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	25	50
Agree	22	44
Neutral	1	2
Disagree	1	2
Strongly disagree	1	2
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 50 % of respondents strongly agrees that they carried several activities during the working day; 44 % agrees that create stress , only 2% have neutral and rest disagreed .

Table 8 Distribution Family life problems

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	12	24
Agree	30	60
Neutral	4	8
Disagree	2	4
Strongly disagree	2	4
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: In the table 60% of the respondents agrees that taking college work disturbs their family life. And 24 % strongly agrees that. 4 % have neutral opinion and 4 % have disagreement towards the statement, 4 % strongly disagrees.

Table 9 Distribution pleasing working environment

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	8	16
Agree	34	68
Neutral	4	8
Disagree	3	6
Strongly disagree	1	2
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: The table shows 68% respondents agrees that they have stress due to the lack of pleasing working environment, and 16% respondents strongly agrees only 2% have strongly disagreement towards the statement .

Table 10 Distribution Inter personal Conflicts

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	5	10
Agree	30	60
Neutral	8	16
Disagree	5	10
Strongly disagree	2	4
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: The above table depicts 60% of the respondents agreed that there exists interpersonal conflicts among the groups which they belongs., 10 % have strong agreement towards the statement, 16% have neutral response and only 4% have strong disagreement.

Table 10 Distribution contradictory instructions

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	21	42
Agree	20	40
Neutral	3	6
Disagree	5	10
Strongly disagree	1	2
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: The above table shows that 42% of the respondents strongly agree that they are facing contradictory instructions by the management. 40 % agrees it. Only 10 % have disagreement towards it and 2 % have strong disagreement.

Table 11 Distribution Insufficient Time for Research

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	9	18
Agree	33	66
Neutral	5	10
Disagree	2	4
Strongly disagree	1	2
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 66% of the respondents agrees to insufficient time to carry out research work. 18 % strongly agree that they do not get enough time to carry research work. 10% have neutral response, 1 % of the respondents strongly disagrees it.

Table 12 Distribution Lack of time for Domestic Activities

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	15	30
Agree	26	52
Neutral	6	12
Disagree	2	4
Strongly disagree	1	2
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: The above table reveals that 52 % of the respondents agrees that they suffer from the lack of time for adjusting domestic activities. 30% of the respondents strongly agrees to it. 12% have neutral response and 1% of the respondents have strongly disagreed to the statement.

Table 13 Distribution Lack of proper Rapport with Family

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	9	18
Agree	29	58
Neutral	8	16
Disagree	1	2
Strongly disagree	3	6
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 58% of the respondents suffers stress due to lack proper rapport with family, 6 % and 2% of the respondents says that have no stress due to lack of rapport with family.

Table 14 Distribution Lack of Parental Support

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	2	4
Agree	15	30
Neutral	21	42
Disagree	10	20
Strongly disagree	2	4
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 30% of the respondents agrees that they suffer stress due to lack parental support. 4% have strongly agreed and 42% of the respondents have neutral response. Either creates or not. 4 % have strongly disagreement.

Table 15 Distribution Mental Harassment

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Strongly agree	1	2
Agree	17	34
Neutral	14	28
Disagree	17	34
Strongly disagree	1	2
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 34% of the respondents agreed that they are facing mental harassment at workplace by superiors or colleagues. 34 % of the respondents have disagreement towards this statement; 28 % of the respondents have neutral opinion

Table 16 Distribution Feeling of irritation at class

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Inefficiency in class management	3	6
Lack of communication from students	10	20
Undisciplined attitude of students	37	74
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 74 % of the feels irritated due to the undisciplined attitude of students. 20% feels irritation due to the lack proper communication from students. Only 6 % of the respondents feels due to inefficiency in class management.

Table 16 Distribution Effect of Stress

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Headache	15	30
Migraine	14	28
Lack of sleep	9	18
Anxiety	7	14
Depression	5	10
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation

The table shows that 30% of the respondents suffers from headaches. 28% have migraine problems due to stress. 18% have lack of sleep. 10 % suffers from depression.

Table 17 Distribution Management dealings with stress management

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Conducting refreshing programs	37	74
Reducing work load	8	16
Provision for counselling	3	6
Others	2	4
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: In the above table 74 % of the respondents responded that the management manages their stress by conducting refreshing programs. 16% says that manages through reducing work load only 4 % responded to others.

Table 18 Distribution Coping Mechanism

Options	No of respondents	Percentage
Spending time with family	20	40
Spending time on social media	20	40
Yoga or meditation	5	10
Spending on reading	3	6
Other	2	4
Total	50	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation: From the above table 40 % of the respondents manages their stress by spending time with family, 40% manages by spending time on social media. Only 10% of the respondents depends yoga or meditation for managing stress. 3 % spends on reading.

FINDINGS

- According to the survey results, 42% of the 50 respondents are between the ages of 30 and 40, and 66% are female.
- The majority of the surveyed individuals are married, and the vast majority meet the necessary qualifications.
- Assistant professors constitute most of the respondents.
- 60% of the participants engaged in classes for 3-4 hours consecutively.
- Additionally, 52% of the participants firmly agreed that their workload is excessive.
- The data suggests that stress often leads to job abandonment among educators.
- Throughout the workday, the educators engaged in various tasks.
- Respondents reported that their professional responsibilities negatively impact their personal lives, and the work environment is unpleasant.
- Interpersonal difficulties with colleagues and inconsistent directives from the administration were also noted.
- Educators struggle with insufficient time to manage household responsibilities and prepare lesson plans.
- Participants expressed experiencing stress due to improper family relations and mental harassment from coworkers or superiors.
- Many respondents reported annoyance with students' lack of discipline in the classroom and stress-induced headaches.
- In response, management plans to offer refresher courses to help instructors cope with stress.
- However, the survey indicates that teachers are not receiving the anticipated pay scale.
- The opinions of teachers regarding stress factors and burnout reveal critical insights into the current challenges facing the education system.

DISCUSSIONS

The purpose of this study was to analyze the stress management among Self Financing arts and science college teachers. The study revealed that Self Financing college teachers are facing more stress. The overtime, family management, low salary package and unhealthy working environment are the main reason for stress. Female teachers are not able to manage work life balance properly. It leads to health issues also. Hence, suitable measures should be taken to manage stress by providing certain relief measures within the institution itself.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Appropriate measures should be taken to reduce the excessive workload of teachers.
- Flexible work schedules should be considered to help mitigate family-related issues.
- A proper and transparent work environment should be promoted.
- Fostering positive relationships with colleagues is encouraged.
- Adequate emphasis should be placed on the need for rest.
- Salaries should be commensurate with the teachers' workload.
- Avoiding the assignment of additional tasks, such as extra duties or overtime, is recommended.
- Providing more rejuvenating activities in the workplace can help alleviate stress among college teachers.
- Offering counselling services within reasonable limits can also help minimize stress.
- Encouraging and supporting teachers for their dedication and family management is crucial.

CONCLUSION

This study examines the multifaceted challenges encountered by self-financing arts and science college faculty. It underlines the necessity for customized interventions to enhance their well-being and academic productivity. While these instructors employ diverse coping mechanisms, they also face significant obstacles that can negatively affect their overall productivity and job satisfaction. The research highlights the importance of addressing faculty stress, particularly among marginalized groups such as self-financing college teachers. This is essential to improve the quality of higher education and ensure the long-term viability of the sector. Future research should further investigate the unique experiences of faculty across diverse institutional settings, with a focus on developing comprehensive stress management programs tailored to their specific needs.

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